

THE USE OF POTASSIUM THIOSULPHATE SOLUTION FOR LEACHING OF GOLD FROM DISPOSED CELL PHONES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the leaching of gold from discarded cell phone printed circuit boards (PCBs) using potassium thiosulphate solution as a safer alternative to cyanide. The objectives included analyzing and pre-concentrating the pulverized PCBs, optimizing leaching efficiency, and electrowinning the extracted gold. The PCBs were pulverized and analyzed using energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDX) to confirm the gold content. Magnetic separation removed ferrous components, followed by treatment with trioxonitrate (V) and hydrogen tetraoxosulphate (VI) acids to eliminate base metals like copper and zinc. The residue was then leached with the thiosulphate solution with various concentrations of copper (II) sulphate and ammonia added to enhance gold dissolution. The leachate was used for electrowinning, and the gold content was analyzed with SEM/EDX. The result showed maximum gold dissolution of 0.88 ppm. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of gold in the electrowinning deposit. The study concludes that gold can be extracted from electronic waste using this method, offering a viable alternative for precious metal recovery and improving electronic waste management.

Keywords: E-wastes, PCBs, Thiosulphate, Precious metals, Leaching

INTRODUCTION

The focus on extracting precious metals has shifted towards electronic waste (E-waste) due to rapid technological advancement, leading to significant environmental concerns. In 2018, approximately 50 million tons of E-waste was generated globally, with an expected annual growth of 3-5% (WEF, 2020). While countries like Japan, Germany, and Switzerland have established effective recycling systems, many developing countries in Africa still face challenges in managing E-waste (Wu *et al.*, 2017)

E-wastes pose significant environmental risks when disposed of in landfills, as their leachates can contaminate soil and groundwater (Luo *et al.*, 2011). Incineration of E-waste generates harmful compounds, including estrogenic substances and toxic emissions like polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins, dibenzofurans, and polybrominated diphenyl ethers, which are detrimental to both human health and the ecosystem (Duan *et al.*, 2012).

Fly and bottom ashes from the incineration of electronic waste contain heavy metals such as lead and mercury, which can contaminate the atmosphere when vaporized (Long *et al.*, 2013). Additionally, the presence of non-

biodegradable plastics poses further environmental concerns. Post-processing challenges include the disposal of toxic effluents from cyanide leaching and the release of harmful gases, like nitrogen oxides from processes such as aqua regia leaching.

Despite environmental concerns, electronic waste (E-waste) is a vital secondary source for extracting base and precious metals from printed circuit boards (PCBs), which comprise 3-6% of total E-waste (Das *et al.* 2009J). The metal content in PCBs is often 10 to 100 times higher than that in traditionally mined ores. Processing E-waste offers economic benefits, reduces environmental damage from mining, and provides materials for various industries. The short lifespan (2.54 to 2.67 years) of electronic devices, such as mobile phones (Statista, 2023), contributes to growing E-waste, suggesting that metal recovery from E-waste will remain relevant. A notable example of E-waste recycling for economic development is the Tokyo 2020 Medal Project, which produced medals entirely from recycled metals (Moriguchi, 2020).

Hydrometallurgical processing of gold has enhanced the extraction industry by reducing environmental pollution and capital costs. This method involves a chemical pre-treatment of waste PCBs, followed by leaching with a suitable lixiviant. The resulting leachate is then separated to produce single metallic solutions for extracting elemental metals (Jadhav and Hocheng, 2015).

Cyanide is a cost-effective lixiviant for gold leaching but poses toxicity and environmental risks. In contrast, thiosulphate solutions, such as ammonium and sodium thiosulphate, are environmentally friendly and easier to handle, though less effective (Ha *et al.*, 2010; Camellino *et al.*, 2015; Jeon *et al.*, 2017, 2018; Petter *et al.*, 2015; Kasper and Veit, 2018; Ha *et al.*, 2014; Kasper *et al.*, 2015; Mahandra *et al.*, 2021; Huang *et al.*, 2022). This study aims to analyze pulverized printed circuit boards (PCBs) for

gold content, evaluate the leaching efficiency of alternative lixiviant, and recover gold from the leachate through electrochemical deposition.

base metal leaching with 1.5 M HNO₃ and 2.5 M H₂SO₄ to extract metals like iron, copper, and zinc.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Process Involved in this Study.

Table 1: Parameters Used in the Leaching Process with Potassium Thiosulphate

S2O3 ²⁻ -Conc. (150 ml)	NH ₃ Conc. (50 ml)	Copper Conc. (50 ml)	Solid/Liquid Ratio	pH	Temperature (°C)	Time (hrs.)
0.2 M	0.3 M	10 mmM	1/25	10.7 – 11.3	~ 28	3
0.15 M	0.2 M	15 mmM	1/25	10.7 – 11.3	~ 28	3
0.1 M	0.1 M	20 mmM	1/25	10.7 – 11.3	~ 28	3

Note: All samples diluted 20x

METHODOLOGY

A block diagram summarizing the process is shown in Figure 1.

Preparation/Reduction and Characterization of PCBs

Cell phones were disassembled to remove polymeric frames, batteries and isolate the printed circuit boards (PCBs) from other components (Plate 1). The PCBs were then reduced to 3-5 mm pieces and pulverized using a Standard Rocklabs Pulverizer (model no. CRC 3E, with serial no. 1288 and Ring Mill type). Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analyzed the elemental composition of the crushed samples. Subsequent steps involved magnetic separation and initial

Leaching of Pulverized PCBs

After initial base metal leaching, the residue was dried in preparation for leaching with potassium thiosulphate solution, leveraging the established leaching capacities of various thiosulphates (Petter *et al.*, 2015; Kasper and Veit, 2018; Ha *et al.*, 2010; Camelino *et al.*, 2015; Jeon *et al.*, 2018; Ficeriova *et al.*, 2011). Three sample solutions were prepared using 10 grams of PCBs, with copper (II) sulphate and ammonia added as additives, and their concentrations, along with that of the thiosulphate, were varied as detailed in Table 1.

Electrowinning of Leachate

The electrowinning process was carried out with the aid of the AutoLab PGStat 204 equipment at the Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo

University (OAU), Ile-Ife, while the analysis of the sample after the electrodeposition process was carried out using the Scanning Electron Microscope/Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy equipment also at the Department of Materials Science and Engineering.

In the electrowinning procedure, a stainless-steel sample served as the working electrode for depositing gold from a solution with a concentration of 0.88 ppm, derived from leaching printed circuit boards using potassium thiosulphate (After Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy carried out at the Center for Energy Research and Development, OAU). A silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) reference electrode and a platinum counter electrode were used. Cyclic voltammetry identified a suitable electrodeposition potential of -1.8V, followed by a 3-hour chronoamperometry experiment. Afterward, the working electrode was removed, rinsed, and prepared for Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis.

Plate 1: (a) Disposed Cell Phones (b) Isolated Polymeric Frames (c) Removal of Batteries

Table 2: EDX Result of the Crushed PCBs

ELEMENTS	WEIGHT%	ATOMIC%
O K	35.50	68.42
Si K	12.50	13.72
Ca K	4.41	3.39
Cu K	1.52	0.74
Br L	18.66	7.20
Sr L	5.81	2.05
Sb L	7.76	1.97
Ba L	3.58	0.80
Hf L	7.04	1.22
Au L	1.37	0.21

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result of EDX Analysis on Pulverized PCBs

The Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis of the pulverized sample is summarized in Table 2, which lists the elements detected at a specific location on the pelletized sample. The analysis showed that gold constitutes approximately 1.37 wt.% of the area analyzed (EDS Spot

1), indicating its presence in discarded printed circuit boards from cell phones, thereby supporting the feasibility of this research.

Result of AAS Analysis Carried-out after Leaching with Potassium Thiosulphate.

Table 3 presents the results of Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy analyses on three 10 g samples of printed circuit boards (PCBs) after base metal leaching, using potassium thiosulphate as lixiviant, with ammonia and copper (II) sulphate as additives. From Table 3, Sample 3, with concentrations of 0.2 M potassium thiosulphate, 0.3 M ammonia, and 10 mM copper (II) sulphate, achieved the highest gold extraction at 0.88 ppm. In contrast, using 0.1 M potassium thiosulphate, 0.1 M ammonia, and 20 mM copper (II) sulphate yielded 0.76 ppm. Increasing the concentrations of potassium thiosulphate and ammonia while decreasing copper (II) sulphate to 15 mM resulted in a slight decrease in extraction to 0.74 ppm. Ultimately, the ideal combination significantly increased gold extraction by approximately 19%.

Aylmore and Muir (2001) reported that concentrated thiosulphate solutions (> 0.1 M) disintegrate more slowly than diluted ones (< 0.01 M), which could explain the higher gold extraction rates observed. To prevent the oxidation of thiosulphate into tetrathionate during the gold extraction process (Equation 1), it is essential to maintain the stability of the thiosulphate.

Table 3: AAS Result of the Digested Sample using Potassium Thiosulphate*

Sample	Abs	Conc. (ppm)	Actual conc. (ppm)	Standard deviation
1	0.009	0.76	0.76	± 0.0005
2	0.009	0.74	0.74	± 0.0005
3	0.011	0.88	0.88	± 0.0007

The roles of ammonia and copper (II) sulphate as additives in the thiosulphate leaching process are well-documented in various studies (Grosse *et al.*, 2003; Ha *et al.*, 2014; Jeffrey and Breuer, 2002; Oraby *et al.*, 2014). Copper (II) ions (Cu²⁺) function as a catalyst, facilitating the leaching process but are eventually reduced to cuprous ions (Cu⁺), which leads to their degradation and the formation of tetrathionate as in equation 2.

Ammonium ions stabilize the copper ions in their cupric state, enhancing the rate of gold dissolution from printed circuit boards. This stabilization is crucial for maximizing the overall gold dissolution reactions involved in the extraction process as represented below.

Result of Electrowinning of the Leachate with Maximum Gold Dissolution

The stainless-steel sample, used as the working electrode after electrodeposition, was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy. The micrograph (Plate 2) at $\times 1000$ magnification revealed nucleation at various locations. EDX analysis identified the constituents of these nuclei, as shown in Table 4, including additional elements deposited alongside gold, which were present in the leachate due to gold's high reduction potential.

Plate 2: Micrograph for EDX Analysis of Selected Spot.

Table 4: EDX Result Showing Gold from Spot 1

Element	Line	Weight %	Atomic %
Si K	K	0.63	2.56
Fe K	K	2.98	6.14
Cu K	K	15.62	28.27
Mo L	L	17.79	21.33
Eu L	L	3.19	2.14
Tb L	L	12.17	8.81
Hf L	L	44.73	28.82
Au L	L	1.08	0.63
Hg L	L	1.80	1.03

CONCLUSION

The analysis of pulverized printed circuit boards (PCBs) from used cell phones revealed significant amounts of gold

that can be economically extracted. Using Potassium thiosulphate to leach gold from pre-concentrated PCBs, the maximum leached amount was found to be 0.88 ppm. Gold from the highest leachate was then electrodeposited onto a stainless-steel working electrode at 1.8 V for 3 hours, with subsequent analysis confirming successful gold deposition through SEM/EDX.

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